

SIMULTANEOUS MULTI-FREQUENCY DIELECTRIC ANALYSIS OF THE POLYMERIZATION PROCESS OF ANIONIC POLYAMIDE 6

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Keywords: Dielectric Analysis (DEA), Anionic Ring-opening Polymerization (AROP), Anionic Polyamide 6 (aPA6), Cure Monitoring, Thermoplastic Resin-Transfer-Molding (T-RTM)

ABSTRACT

The demand for sustainable material concepts is increasing more and more. One possible concept is the use of thermoplastic fiber reinforced composite components. The processing of anionic polyamide 6 offers both advantages in the processing of low-viscosity melts and improved material properties due to a very high degree of crystallization and simultaneously very long molecular chains. The processing of this anionic polyamide 6 (aPA6) in thermoplastic resin transfer molding (T-RTM) is already state of the art. Due to the extremely high sensitivity to moisture the material is only processed under inert gas atmospheres. Because moisture decreases the reactivity of the chemicals involved in the curing process there is demand for a measuring method to determine the state of cure during the production process. A well-known method is the measurement of the temperature curve during anionic polymerization. Due to the exothermic characteristics of the reaction this method allows a statement about the conversion. However, this method is only used on a laboratory scale. An integration of this method into the T-RTM process has not been successful so far.

Dielectric Analysis (DEA) provides the means to perform online measurements inside the melt to determine the state of the material. By the use of a newly developed advanced measurement system it is possible to acquire measurement results of multiple excited frequencies simultaneously. This provides unprecedented depth of information compared to state of the art DEA analysis. In this paper the proposed technology was applied to a generic processing method and the results compared to conventional temperature measurements. The results and findings of these trials are discussed in detail and a new method for analyzing the curing process is proposed. After successful testing the dielectric measurement system was also used in a real-world production environment to show the capabilities of the new measurement system.

1 INTRODUCTION

The increase in the worldwide production of plastics since the 1950s leads to the problem of growing waste. To deal with this issue the demand for sustainable material concepts in many industries is increasing rapidly [1].

One possibility to meet the increasing demand is the use of thermoplastic fiber reinforced composite components. Anionic polyamide 6 (aPA6) combines the advantages of a low viscosity melt during the production process with superior material properties due to a very high degree of crystallization with simultaneously very long molecular chains.

The growing use of fiber reinforced composites has given rise to many new processing technologies. Even though the remarkable characteristics of these components have been proven in countless studies the area of process control is still a field of ongoing research. One of the major problems is the monitoring of the curing behavior of the used matrix materials around the load carrying fibers.

Dielectric Analysis (DEA) has proven to be an important tool in various industry and research sectors. Examples are the examination of the dispersion behavior of colloidal particles in solutions and suspensions [2, 3], the investigation of the properties of biological tissue [4-6] or the cure monitoring of plastic processing technologies as RTM or SMC/BMC [7, 8]. With the use of an unconventional

approach of this technique to maximize the information density introduced by Geinitz et al in [9], it was possible to perform dielectric measurements on aPA6 to characterize the different stages of the curing process during the in-situ polymerization. The results of these experiments as well as first interpretations are presented in this paper

2 ANIONIC POLYMERIZATION OF POLYAMIDE

The reaction of the activated anionic ring-opening polymerization (AROP) of ϵ -caprolactam is shown in Fig. 1. For initiation, the catalytically active sodium caprolactamate forms a growth center together with a n -acyllactam. A free caprolactam molecule reacts with the growth center and opens its ring between the carbonyl group and the secondary nitrogen. The compound in the growth center between nitrogen and carbon is also opened and attacks the carbonyl group of the opened caprolactam. Thus the ring of the caprolactam molecule is opened and completely incorporated. The negatively charged nitrogen in the resulting oligomer now attacks the carbonyl group of a free caprolactam molecule. This is again split between carbonyl group and secondary nitrogen and then bound to the nitrogen anion. The proton exchange with the monomer binds the monomer to the chain and a new lactam anion is generated. This process is repeated until no free monomers are left. A special termination reaction does not occur. [10]

This reaction mechanism is very susceptible to external influences. Even small amounts of humidity or water can influence the conversion [11, 12]. In this paper, the suitability of the DEA method for the online characterization of AROP is investigated and evaluated.

Figure 1: Anionic polymerization of polyamide [10].

2.1 Experimentation

For the experiments, a low pressure T-RTM injection machine of the Fraunhofer institute for chemical technologies (ICT) was used. Evacuation and impinging the two tanks of the machine with inert gas avoids the influence of humidity on the contents. One tank contains a mixture of ϵ -caprolactam and the activator C20, in the other tank the ϵ -caprolactam is mixed with catalyst C10. As soon as both material mixtures are brought together the reaction starts. Experiments were conducted with two separate setups, in form of beaker experiments to evaluate the basic chemical processes during the polymerization and in a T-RTM processing setup to achieve results close to the actual manufacturing environment. Figure 2 shows the schematic test setup.

2.1.1 Beaker Trials

For the beaker experiments, the components are melted and heated to 150 °C. For these experiments the melt temperature is equal to the beaker temperature, because the melt inside the beaker cannot heat up as quickly as in the T-RTM production of thin plates.

The machine injects 300 grams of the mixture into a beaker. The DEA signal and the temperature is measured simultaneously inside of the beaker. The dielectric sensors were placed in the vicinity of the beaker side surfaces.

Figure 2: Schematic setup of the low pressure T-RTM machine with beaker and mold option.

2.1.2 T-RTM Processing Trials

The measurements were conducted at Fraunhofer ICT using a Dieffenbacher press type DCP-G 3600-3200 and a T-RTM tool with dimensions of 900 mm x 550 mm. In the T-RTM processing experiments, the components are heated to 98 °C. The tool is heated to 150 °C to start the anionic polymerization. For the experiments 870 grams of melt are injected into a plate tool, which was evacuated for 60 s before the injection. The manufactured plates have a thickness of 2 mm. Inside the mold the monomers react to polyamide 6 within several seconds up to a few minutes. The dielectric sensor was fixed to the tool surface using heat resistant tape.

2.1.3 Materials

The studies were carried out with the monomer ϵ -caprolactam, the activator Brüggolen C20 and the catalyst Brüggolen C10 from Brüggemann chemicals. Due to the bi-functionality of the activator the ratio between activator and catalyst was kept at a constant ratio of 1:2 for all formulations examined within the test program. In total, measurements were performed with four different formulations. Table 1 shows the different formulations with the according ratio of activator as percentage by weight of the entire probe sample. Water was added to these formulations in 0.02 % steps until a concentration of max. 0.08 % was reached.

Formulation	F1	F2	F3	F4
Ratio of Activator/Catalyst	1.0 %/2.0 %	1.5 %/3.0 %	2.0 %/4.0 %	2.5 %/5.0 %

Table 1: Formulations of the experiments with according ratios of activator and catalyst.

3 DIELECTRIC ANALYSIS

Although it is counted to the thermal analysis methods, DEA occupies a special status among these standard material characterization techniques. DEA is based on the measurement and interpretation of interactions between ions and molecules in a material under test with an external applied electric field [17]. Subsequently, material properties are determined by measuring the reaction current and the corresponding phase angle as a result of an excitation voltage signal. The results with the best signal-to-noise ratio can be achieved by the use of a single frequency sine wave voltage excitation signal [18].

By determining the complex impedance and phase angle, different material properties, such as complex permittivity or ionic conductivity, can be calculated to evaluate the material conditions [15].

Figures 3 and 4 show the measured raw data of impedance magnitude $|Z|$, and the corresponding phase angle θ respectively over the curing cycle of one of the beaker experiments. The according formulas are shown in (1) and (2), where $|V|$ is the absolute value of the excitation voltage and $|I|$ the respective value for the response current. The phase angle θ is calculated from the complex phase angles φ_V and φ_I .

$$|Z| = \frac{|V|}{|I|} \cdot e^{-i\theta} \quad (1)$$

$$\theta = \varphi_V - \varphi_I \quad (2)$$

The absolute permittivity ε of a medium is a measure for the ability of a material to store an electric field in its polarization. Typically, the relative permittivity ε_r is used to describe the behavior of a material, which is the ratio of the absolute permittivity ε to the permittivity of free space ε_0 . Like the absolute permittivity, the relative permittivity is a complex quantity, which is also dependent on the frequency of the applied field. Equation (3) shows the relation between the parameters explained above

$$\varepsilon_r(\omega) = \frac{\varepsilon(\omega)}{\varepsilon_0} = \varepsilon_r'(\omega) - i \cdot \varepsilon_r''(\omega) \quad (3)$$

While the real part ε_r' represents the amount of amplitude in phase with the applied field and is related to the energy stored within the medium, the imaginary part ε_r'' is the amount of energy phase shifted by 90° and related to the dissipation of energy within the medium. Due to the measuring of the change in the a capacitance both the real part of the permittivity $\varepsilon_r'(\omega)$ as well as the imaginary part $\varepsilon_r''(\omega)$ commonly referred to as loss factor can be determined. The loss factor is calculated according to formula (4) where ω is the angular frequency and A/d is a sensor specific value.

$$\varepsilon_r''(\omega) = \frac{I \cdot \cos \theta}{V \cdot \omega \cdot \varepsilon_0} \cdot (A/d)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

The imaginary part of the permittivity therefor allows an analysis of the converted energy during the curing process of aPA6.

Figure 3: Impedance magnitude data of a curing process of APA6 formulation F4 monitored with a multi-frequency dielectric measurement systems.

Figure 4: Impedance magnitude data of a curing process of APA6 formulation F4 monitored with a multi-frequency dielectric measurement systems.

In order to adequately evaluate manufacturing and curing processes, a broadband measurement of the electric variables is necessary as the permittivity is highly frequency dependent. Especially the impact of polarization mechanisms at low frequencies affect the loss factor. [19]

Unfortunately, commercially available systems achieve spectroscopic results only by the use of an iterative frequency sweep. To overcome this limitation an advanced dielectric monitoring device was developed, which offers the possibility of spectroscopic examinations combined with an extremely high measuring point density. The actual simultaneous recording of up to 25 different applied frequencies reduces significantly the measurement time per measurement point. Thus creating the potential to

analyze extremely dynamic reactive systems in detail even at low frequencies. In addition, the measurement points are recorded time-synchronously for all frequencies as shown by Geinitz et al. [9], allowing immediate spectroscopic analysis. To achieve this high information density a specialized excitation signal and a circuit layout capable for broadband measurements are needed. With respect to the excitation signal, studies have proven that a multisine signal offers several advantages over other multi frequency signals, like binary sequences or chirp signals [20]. Many circuit layouts have been presented over the years, extensively documented by Blythe et al. [21]. With the use of a transimpedance amplifier a lossless current to voltage conversion over a wide range of frequencies is possible. Both, the excitation signal and the circuit layout combined opens up the potential to realize material characterization and condition monitoring to far unprecedented extend in the laboratory as well as in the process environment.

4 COMPARISON TO STATE OF THE ART

In most production processes the degree of cure is the parameter of interest because it enables the control of production cycles. In order to monitor the curing cycle and in consequence ensure the quality of manufactured parts the temperature method has proven to be a reliable measure.

The maximum temperature rise ΔT_{max} of the exothermic polymerization can be calculated using formula 5

$$\Delta T_{max} = \frac{\Delta H}{c_p(x)} \quad (5)$$

For this particular case $\Delta H = 15.9 \text{ kJ/mol}$ and $c_p = 313.8 \text{ J/(K} \cdot \text{mol)}$. This yields a maximum temperature rise of $\Delta T_{max} = 51 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [23, 24].

Figure 4 shows the results of the temperature measurements for formulation F4 with no added water as a dashed-dotted line. The temperature measurement shows a steep increase over the first 30 s until a final temperature of approximately 204 °C is reached. The temperature remains at this level for the rest of the experiment without significant changes.

Additionally, 5 discrete measurements of the dielectric loss factor have been included in figure 4. In contrast to the temperature curve those measurements show a very specific behavior for different frequencies. While the lower frequencies, f(3) and f(10), have a maximum at around 65 s and appear to be rising towards the end of the measurement period, the higher frequencies, f(13) through f(18), reach their maximum much sooner and show declining behavior over time.

Looking at this graph it becomes obvious that a conventional dielectric analysis of discrete frequencies during the polymerization process will yield no results which are comparable to the more general approach of monitoring the exothermic behavior of the entire sample by temperature measurements.

The frequency dependent characteristics of the DEA measurements can be visualized over the entire experimental range. Figure 5 shows the maximum values of the loss factor measurements over the spectrum of excited frequencies. For the lower half of excited frequencies, the maximum value of the loss factor measurements shows declining behavior. Superimposed to which an offset depending on the water content can be observed. For the upper half of the excited frequencies a change in the course of the graphs can be noted. The turning point appears for higher excited frequencies with increasing water content. For the 18th excited frequency all 5 curves show the same maximum value for the measurements of the dielectric loss factor.

This yields that a determination of credible absolute values from measurements with a single randomly selected excitation frequency is not possible due to the frequency dependent behavior of the measurement system. Additionally, the influence of added water to the sample under test can be taken as an example for occurring environmental influences on the measurements. Amounts smaller than 0.1 % by weight of the entire sample, between F4-2550 0.00% H₂O and F4-2550 0.08 H₂O, can cause differences in the measured absolute values of more than two decades. Nevertheless, the clearly visible frequency dependent characteristics of the material can be visualized by exploiting the superior capabilities of the previously described multi-frequency measurement system which allows a simultaneous analysis over a wide frequency range.

Figure 4 Comparison of the temperature measurement with the curves of the dielectric loss factor for several different frequencies for formulation F4 with no added water.

Figure 5 Maximum values of the dielectric loss factor for the different excited frequencies for formulation F4-2550.

Figure 6 shows the dielectric loss factor ϵ_r'' during the beaker experiment with formulation F4 with no added water as a heat map over time and frequency. This representation allows a depiction of all measured frequencies in one graph. The graph is divided into two areas which are clearly separated from each other. This is shown by the black line. The temporarily first part can be seen in the high frequency region starting at approximately 30 kHz. On the other side, a part with a higher absolute value can be seen in the lower frequency region. Starting approx. 40 s into the experiment this area extends its intensity form an initially small frequency bandwidth to a maximum frequency related extension at around 65 s, which was described in figure 5 before. Past this point the loss factor decreases gradually over all measured frequencies. The relatively high noise in the lower frequency region can be traced back to electrode polarization of the used capacitive sensor. Nevertheless, the imaging of the measurements enables new possibilities of process analysis

Figure 6: Dielectric loss factor during a beaker experiment with formulation F4 with no added water.

The dielectric loss factor is a measure for the amount of energy which is dissipated in form of heat during the experiment. By summing up this value over time and the separate frequency areas the respective exothermic contributions to the overall process can be determined. Figure 7 shows the analysis results of the summed loss factor curves for formulation F4 with no water added. This exemplary analysis can be applied to all other conducted experiments, yielding the same results. The solid line shows the sum over all measured frequencies, while the dashed line shows the high frequency part and the dashed-dotted line shows the low frequency part respectively. The two frequency areas sum

up to the final graph. The separation between low and high frequency area was done along the frequency with the minimal value of the dielectric loss factor ϵ_r'' for every measurement along the time series. These graphs provide proof of a staged process during the cure of the anionic polyamide 6. While the high frequency reaction starts immediately after the injection into the beaker, the low frequency reaction does not fully start until 45 s into the polymerization process. Although the absolute value of the sum for the low frequency area is higher than of the high frequency area, this effect is mainly due to electrode polarization and has to be omitted for the qualitative analysis of the reaction. It is also interesting to notice that the first reaction shows almost no further increase as soon as the second reaction takes over to dominate the graph. Comparing these graphs to the temperature measurements it can be noticed that the exothermic temperature increase is mainly caused during the reaction observable in the high frequency area. The rate of increase of which reduces around 30 s into the experiment. Nevertheless, the temperature measured inside the beaker stays at more than 200 °C (see figure 5). This indicates that the second part of the reaction generates enough heat to keep the temperature inside the beaker at a constant level during the entire polymerization process

Figure 7 Summed Loss Factors of formulation F4 with no water added for the entire frequency band-width (solid), the high frequency region (dashed), and the low frequency region without noise (dot-dashed).

Figure 8 Comparison of temperature curves with the summed curves of the dielectric loss factor for formulation F4 with different water content.

Figure 8 shows the according temperatures for the beaker experiments of formulation F4 and additionally the curves for the experiments with added water. The dashed and double dotted lines show the sum of the dielectric loss factor over the entire frequency bandwidth of the dielectric measurements plotted over time. As just explained, these curves represent the energy conversion during the chemical reaction because they sum up the dissipated energy over the entire measurement bandwidth during the polymerization.

While the temperature measurements show a steady increase over the reaction time until a final temperature of approximately 204 °C is reached, the dielectric measurements indicate the start of a second reaction some time into the ongoing curing process for every single measurement. The start of this second reaction is also clearly dependent on the amount of added water. The more water was inserted into the monomer containers of the low pressure injection machine the more the second rise is delayed in the graphs. This not linearly rising delay with on the other hand linearly increasing water content was already observed by Wendel et al [12]. It can be noticed that the start of the second reaction always takes place right after the maximum temperature in the beaker has been reached.

While all five graphs of the dielectric measurements show a similar behavior for the first part of the reaction, the slope decreases with the amount of water added to the monomers. Although the added water delays the start of the second reaction, it can be observed that the kink in the dielectric curves happens at the same level of the summed loss factor for all five experiments. The temperature experiments show the same results by the identical maximum temperature of the measurements. Because the temperature method can only measure the generated heat as a consequence of the exothermic reaction

it is not a suitable tool to analyze the ongoing reaction in a detailed and spectroscopic manner. The shown dielectric measurements on the other hand can be subdivided into the single frequency components to examine the interactions and processes during the reaction in more detail. The interpretation of the findings of the beaker experiments indicates that the dielectric analysis yields more sophisticated results than the temperature method is capable of, because it is able to access information related directly to the ongoing chemical reactions and not only the resulting heat. This information cannot be accessed via a two dimensional graph though. To fully exploit the acquired information, the dimension of frequency needs to be taken into account as well.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

As described at the beginning of this paper, it is possible to perform simultaneous spectroscopic analyses of a sample under test. Taking into account the learnings from the previous chapter a new representation of the curing process was suggested. After a correlation between the state of the art temperature method and the newly developed DEA system has been shown, the results of previously analyzed formulation F4 can be compared and the influences of the added water content on the results of the beaker experiments can be evaluated. Finally, an application example of this measurement technique is given for the production process of thin plates using T-RTM.

5.1 Beaker Experiments

Figures 10–13 show the results of the beaker experiments for formulation F4 with rising water content in the monomer tanks, from 0.02 % to 0.08 % by weight.

The start of the second reaction, which is equivalent to the slope change in the sum of the dielectric measurements and therefore with the reaching of the maximum temperature inside the beaker, can be found in the 2D graphs as an edge at the low end of the frequency bandwidth. The more water gets added to the monomer tanks the more the start of the reaction gets delayed. Figure 9 shows the starting point of the second reaction as a function of added water in percent by weight. For the first three concentrations the solid curve for formulation F4-2550 shows an almost linear increase in time. But including the last two values as well the behavior is better described as an exponential curve. In comparison to the solid curve the dashed line shows the same parameters for the weaker and slower formulation F1-1020. There are only two measurements for this formulation because an amount of 0.02 % water is sufficient to completely prevent the polymerization process. It is to assume that for the remaining three formulations the starting point of the second reaction will be located in between the curves for F1 and F4. Nevertheless, the proof of this statement will be part of ongoing research in this field.

The same behavior can be observed for the frequency extension of the second reaction. For the initial measurement without water with an extension to some 22 kHz, it rises to almost 100 kHz for the measurement with 0.06 % water content (see figure 12). Another interesting observation is the temporal extend of this part. With increasing water content, it takes up more time. For the last measurement with 0.08 % water it has not even reached a maximum at the end of the 300 s measurement but appears to be still rising (see figure 13).

Figure 9: Starting points of the second reaction as a function of added water for formulations F1-1020 (dashed) and F4-2550 (solid).

Figure 10: Dielectric loss factor during a beaker experiment of F4-2550 with 0.02 % added water.

Figure 11: Dielectric loss factor during a beaker experiment of F4-2550 with 0.04 % added water.

Figure 12: Dielectric loss factor during a beaker experiment of F4-2550 with 0.06 % added water.

Figure 13: Dielectric loss factor during a beaker experiment of F4-2550 with 0.08 % added water.

The first reaction shows also a temporal behavior in the occurrence of its maximum with adding of water. In comparison to the larger second reaction the first reaction shows a very similar course of events over all experiments. Initially the measurements indicate a broadband spread of the reaction which minimizes until a frequency-spread-wise minimum is reached at the same time the reaction reaches its local maximum. After this point the reaction spreads out again to the initial frequency span, but the overall loss factor value declines. This behavior is most dominantly shown in figure 11 (water content 0.04 %) where the maximum is reached after 30 s.

From experience it is known that the ring-opening reaction starts as soon as the two components are in contact with each other. For this particular formulation the curing time is empirically determined to be less than two minutes. This information can be used to proof that the polymerization can be mainly observed in the high frequency part of the spectrum.

Another interesting observation is the influence of water on the absolute value of the magnitude of the dielectric loss factor. As previously show in figure 5 an offset is generated the more water gets added. At its maximum extend the difference in magnitude between F4-2550 0.00 H₂O and F4-2550 0.08 H₂O is more than two decades. This connection is related to the conductive results of the reaction of the monomer ϵ -caprolactam, activator and catalyst with water. The added dipoles contribute to an offset in the occurring maximum value of the dielectric loss factor. On the other hand, the maximum value of the 18th excited frequency, which is the center frequency of the first occurring reaction is almost at the same level for all analyzed formulations. This observation leads to the assumption that this prior reaction shows the same characteristics despite the changing water content.

5.2 In-mold Application

Figure 11 shows the resulting loss factor heat map for a measurement of formulation F3 with 0.04 % added water inside a T-RTM tool. As described earlier the hollow tool was evacuated for 60 s before the melt was injected. At the injection point the high frequency signal starts to rise to a local maximum value at approx. 75 s. With the end of the first reaction the second low frequency reaction starts to dominate the measurement. A clear maximum in the second reaction as it appears in the beaker experiments is not distinguishable from the results. After some 165 s the graph shows a reduction in the signal value for the low frequency part of the graph which is also visible in the graphs of the beaker experiments.

Altogether the in-mold measurement shows great similarities to the graphs of the beaker experiments, which can be taken as an indication that the experimental setup works also for in-mold DEA measurements. Nevertheless, more research needs to be conducted in the area of curing analysis of thin plates to evaluate the results of the in-mold experiments in more detail. The detailed relation and exact quantification of the differences, like thermodynamic effects for example due to a larger surface area, between the more fundamental beaker setup and real world tools remain part of ongoing research.

Figure 14: Dielectric loss factor during the T-RTM production process of a thin plate made of formulation F3 with 0.04 % added water.

4 CONCLUSION

The results presented in this work show the possibility of the online monitoring of the anionic ring opening polymerization process of aPA6 by the means of dielectric analysis. It could be shown that a classical approach of selecting one particular excitation frequency for DEA does not yield interpretable results for this complex and coherent process. By accessing information from multiple frequency related processes simultaneously it was possible to produce images of the polymerization as they have not been presented yet. Even though the measurement technique allows far more insight into the ongoing reaction further research has to be performed in the field of investigating the curing process. The separation into two different parts has not been observed before and could not be seen in the temperature measurements. One possible explanation is that during the polymerization also a crystallization occurs in the material. The low frequency region which is more likely to excite larger and heavier structures, like crystals could be a measure for the degree of crystallization and the length of the polymer chains. The high frequency excitations are more likely to interact with smaller and lighter elements, like single molecules and yet to be polymer chains. This leads to the thesis that this area of excitations could be representing the polymerization process. Another still unsolved question is the determination of a clear curing point. With a distinct point or criterion, a more sophisticated process control strategy could be implemented for many industrial processes, like the mentioned T-RTM. By this the quality of manufactured parts could be improved as well as energy consumption of this energy intensive production process could be reduced.

With the developed system it is possible to evaluate the ongoing processes in many different physical and chemical systems in a depth which has not been able before. Because of the simultaneous acquisition of several frequency components it is possible to gain access to frequency related information which is not accessible with conventional measurement techniques. The here presented data leads to several other possible fields of application for this measurement technique, including the determination of water content in samples, contamination with parasitic components in the materials and even aging effects on the specimen.

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